

investigated can be arranged according to the decreasing magnitude of their effect in protecting the enzyme against destruction as follows: $\text{NaF} > \text{NaCl} > \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{NaNO}_3$. The divalent cation Ca is more efficient than the monovalent cations Li and Na in protecting the enzyme against destruction.

3. An explanation has been advanced for the salt acceleration of the enzymic hydrolysis of starch. The favourable effects of salts at certain concentrations on the hydrolysis of starch by amylase appears to be associated with the increased protection of the enzyme and the inhibitive action at high salt concentrations with decreased stability of the enzyme under these conditions.

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The Heats of Transition of Triglycerides.

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The property of exhibiting a double melting point has long been regarded as a characteristic of nearly all triglycerides. Several observers* have recorded that these triglycerides melt at a certain temperature, solidify at one slightly higher, and melt again on further heating.

It will be instructive to compare the "melting points" recorded by Efremov (*Ann. Inst. Polyt. Ural*, 1927, **6**, 155), Löskit (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, **134**, 137) and Joglekar and Watson (*loc. cit.*). It should be noted that these investigators claim to have purified their specimens with enormous care, Löskit recording 60 crystallisations, while Joglekar proceeded through as many as 40.

* Guth, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1902, **18**, 169; *cf. Z. Biol.*, 1902, **34**, 78; Grün and Schacht, *Ber.*, 1907, **40**, 1770; *cf. Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 3692; Bömer *Z. Nat. Genussm.*, 1907, **14**, 97; 1909, **16**, 362; Bömer and Limprich, *ibid.*, 1913, **18**, 373; Kremann and Schoulz-Graz, *Monatsh.*, 1912, **33**, 1063; Smits and Bokhorst, *Proc. Acad. Wetensch.*, 1913, **18**, 681; Bokhorst, *Dissertation*, Amsterdam, 1916; Nicolet, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1920, **12**, 741; Grün, *Ber.*, 1921, **54B**, 2909; Klimont, *Oest. Chem. Ztg.*, 1922, **25**, 22; Joglekar and Watson, *Chem. und Med.*, 1928, **47**, 365.

TABLE I.

	Laurin.	Myristin.	Palmitin.	Stearin.
I. Stable form.				
(a) Joglekar and Watson	46·2	56·5	65·6	71·8
(b) Löske	46·4	56·5	64·8	71·8
(c) Efremov	67·5	69·3
II. Mittel modification.				
(b) Löske	...	48·5	55·0	65·4
(c) Efremov	48·4-53·8	53·2-55·2
III. Metastable form.				
(a) Joglekar and Watson	18·0	33·0	46·2	55·0
(b) Löske	36·4	47·0	45·0	55·0
(c) Efremov	48·4	53·2

EXPERIMENTAL.

The present investigation is founded entirely on the following fundamental assumptions:

(1) Triglycerides exist only in two forms.

(2) The metastable solid, obtained on sudden cooling, could be regarded as a pure phase. It will be referred to in this paper as the metastable form.

Heats of Solution of Triglycerides.

If it be granted as exceedingly probable that the glycerides exist in the pure stable form in solution, it would be of interest to measure the heats of the solution of the two forms of each triglyceride in various organic solvents and from the results thus obtained calculate the heat of transition of one form into the other.

To this end in view a twin calorimetric arrangement was set up. The attainment of very high degree of accuracy was never attempted.

The apparatus consisted of two small silvered vacuum flasks similar in size and shape, supported on rubber stoppers on a common wooden mount with a card-board partition between, the whole assemblage slipping into a wooden box. The flasks were closed by stoppers through which passed (a) at the centre, a propeller stirrer of glass, (b) on one side, away from the neighbouring twin, a heater of Constantan

wire mounted on a glass tube carrying potential and current leads, and (c) on the other side, one arm of an inverted U-tube of glass through which one end of a multiple thermel of four junctions passed into the flask.

In one of the twins, a glass tube blown out at lower end into a tiny thin bulb for carrying about 0.2 g. of the substance investigated, was inserted through the stopper. The "dummy" flask was also provided with a similar tube closed at the lower end.

Equal volumes of solvent (50 c.c.) were poured into the twins and the corks replaced. The stirrers were driven by tiny wooden pullies of the same diameter, which were geared on to the pulley of a common motor by a single belt going round all the three. The stirrers were started, and the thermocouple was put on to a sensitive suspended coil-mirror galvanometer. The thermel indicated the difference in temperature between the twins prevailing at any instant to an accuracy of about 0.003°. The galvanometer reading was watched, and when it was steady, it was recorded and the system then could be assumed to be compensated for thermal leakages. The bulb in the one calorimeter was then broken. With the progress of solution the temperature in that calorimeter fell as indicated by the moving spot of light. Heat was simultaneously supplied by the passage of an electric current through the heater, until the spot of light was brought back to the zero at start. Being thus a null method, absolute measurements of temperature are not necessary. From the known resistance of the heater, and the potential across it, read on a Weston sub-standard voltmeter included in parallel in the heater circuit, the heat supplied to the calorimeter could be calculated.

The degree of accuracy which this method gives can be seen from the following values obtained for the heat of solution of sodium chloride in water.

TABLE II.

Temp.	Wt. of NaCl. in 50 c.c. H ₂ O.	Expt. value.	Calc. value(x)	Error.
25.5°	1.0151	991.7 cal./g. mol.	987.9	- 3.9
24.7°	0.9440	1007.8	1008.9	- 1.1
25.8°	1.0220	978.2	879.9	- 1.7

(x calculated from the results of Lipsett, Johnson and Maas, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 1940; taking $\partial H / \partial T = 26.4$ cal. per degree.)

TABLE III.

Heat of solution of tristearin.

M. p. 71.4°. Sol. P. = 69.6°

(A) Solvent-toluene.

(a) Form I (stable).			(b) Form II (metastable).		
Wt. in 50 c.c. solvent.	Temp.	Heat of soln.	Wt. in 50 c.c. solvent.	Temp.	Heat of soln.
0.191 g.	24.8°	46.85 cal./g.	0.241 g.	25.9°	31.84 cal./g.
0.210	25.2	46.98	0.205	26.5	31.50
0.205	26.2	46.98	0.220	26.9	31.62
		-----	0.168	26.9	31.64
		46.98 = 47.00			-----
					31.63 = 32.00

The difference between (a) and (b) of 15.4 cal. per g. is equal to the heat of transition.

(B) Solvent-carbon tetrachloride.

0.193	25.5	41.82	0.218	25.8	25.8
0.182	26.2	40.61	0.195	25.5	25.4
		-----			-----
		41.2			25.6

The difference of 15.6 cal. per g. is equal to the heat of transition.

Better concordance could not be obtained as each time a little substance was left over undissolved.

TABLE IV.

Heat of solution of trilaurine.

M. p. = 65.3°. Sol. p. = 64.3°. Solvent = benzene.

(a) Form I (stable).			(b) Form II (metastable).		
Wt. in 50 c.c. solvent.	Temp.	Heat of soln.	Wt. in 50 c.c. solvent.	Temp.	Heat of soln.
0.159 g.	26.3°	49.49 cal./g.	0.168 g.	26.0°	33.80
0.167	26.5	49.25	0.150	26.5	33.89
		-----			-----
		49.33 = 49.3			33.88 = 33.9

The difference of 15.4 cal. per g. is equal to the heat of transition.

The difficulty with laurin is the fact that at laboratory temperature (30°) the metastable solid cannot exist.

So the twin assembly had to be discarded ; one of two flasks was retained, and enclosed in a jacket containing water and the whole was left in a large vacuum flask with ice packing all round. The other junction of thermel was dipping in the jacket water. Where there was a draft observed at the end of the experiment, adequate correction was made for it in the computation of the heat effect.

The new arrangement gave for the heat of solution of NaCl at 30°, 1572 cal. per g. mol., calculated value being 1568 cal.

Heat of solution of trilaurin.

m.p. (stable) 45·8°-46·0°. m. p. (metastable) 18·0°.

TABLE V.

Solvent-toluene.

(a) Form I (stable).			(b) Form II (metastable).		
Wt. in 50 c.c. solvent.	Temp.	Heat of soln.	Wt. in 50 c.c. solvent.	Temp.	Heat of soln.
0·235 g.	1·2°	37·5	0·274 g.	0·5°	21·9
0·254	1·0	37·4	0·272	1·0	28·2
		—	0·258	0·0	23·6
		37·5	0·270	0·0	21·4

The values for the metastable form are very discordant.

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21·6

The principal difficulty was encountered in the rapid transference in the calorimeter of the metastable substance before it could transform ; and the measurement had to be made in as short a time after insertion of substance into calorimeter as is possible, consistent with the attainment of a uniform common temperature by calorimeter, accessories and substance. Such attainment was not quite certain since the period that could be permitted for this temperature equalisation could never exceed 15 minutes, after the lapse of which the liability of the metastable solid spontaneously transforming sets in.

It is remarkable that in the case of laurin too, the 'heat of transition' is in the neighbourhood of 15 cal. per g.

Latent Heats of Fusion.

When the stable form of stearin is heated to its melting point, a liquid is obtained which on sudden cooling gives the metastable solid. Consequently it is reasonable to suppose that stable stearin on melting gives the liquid corresponding to the metastable form; and the same liquid, though at a lower temperature, is obtained on melting the metastable form. If the specific heats of the two forms are not very different, the difference in the latent heats of fusion of the two forms should give the heat of transition of one form into the other.

The aneroid calorimeter has been employed in some very accurate research by Dickinson and Osborne. (*Bull. Bureau of Standards*, 1915, 12, 23). Using the same design twin aneroids were built with enclosed heaters, and each calorimeter had a narrow re-entrant tube at the centre, closed on top, into which one thermel end could readily slip in. The heater was brought out and connected to terminals fixed to a bakelite base, and they dipped in mercury cups when the calorimeter had been put into the jacket. Between the twins was disposed a bakelite moulded partition carrying on one side a radiation thermel for registering the difference in temperature between calorimeter and jacket. This thermel itself was constructed after the manner described by Miss Wilson and collaborators (*Proc. Phys. Soc.*, 1920, 32, 326) by winding No. 40 Constantan wire on a glass frame-work and silver plating all the turns on one side of the frame up to the middle of the longer edges, so that along each of these we get a row of 20-30 silver Constantan junctions.

The substance was kept in one of these calorimeters and some liquid paraffin in the other. Both were heated along with the completely enclosing jacket, the heating of the latter being hand controlled. The working calorimeter was heated a little faster than the dummy and the jacket temperature was made to keep pace with the mean of the temperatures of both calorimeter and dummy. The thermel registering the difference in temperature between calorimeter and dummy was put on the galvanometer and the spot of light watched. This will be slowly creeping in some direction. At the melting point, due to absorption of latent heat the dummy will heat up and the movement of the spot will reverse. When the fusion is complete, the working calorimeter will rise quicker in temperature than the dummy as it was doing in the nearly stages. So the spot will again turn back on its course. The exact time between this double reversal

of the movement of the spot of light gives the time of fusion. From the known resistance of the heater and the potential across it, the heat of fusion is readily computed.

The principal difficulty in the manipulation of this apparatus is confined to the hand control of jacket temperature for maintenance of approximately adiabatic conditions. With suitable alterations and the employment of an automatic control of jacket heater it is expected that this method should yield good results.

The accuracy actually attained can be gauged from the following measurements for the latent heat of fusion of palmitic acid : (52·75), 51·59, 51·43, (53·54), 51·65, 51·68 and 51·58, mean 51·6. This value is 0·6 cal. higher than that obtained by Mrs. Stratton and Partington (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 43, 436).

TABLE VI.

The latent heat of fusion of tristearin.

Wt. of substance taken = 2·843 g.

Form I (stable) ... (62·1) 61·6 61·8 61·4 Mean 61·6

From II (metastable)... 44·2 (40·8) 44·2 43·6 Mean 44·2

Eykman gives 45·7.

Since partial transformation takes place during fusion which occupies 20 to 21 minutes, too low a result is obtained for the labile form.

Using Eykman's value in conjunction with the value obtained here for stable form the difference works out as $61·6 - 45·7 = 15·9$ cal. for 'heat of transition.'

Tripalmitin gave for the stable form a value of about 62·3 cal. for latent heat. The labile form, however, transforms so quickly that no concordant results for its latent heat of fusion could be obtained.

The above results appear to support the assumption that glycerides exist in stable form in solution. The Raman-effect and X-ray diffraction of the two forms of triglycerides are being studied.

SUMMARY.

1. A method employing a double calorimeter has been applied to the determination of the heats of solution of the two modifications of tripalmitin and tristearin in several organic solvents.
2. The difference in the heats of solution of the two forms is constant and equal to the difference in the latent heats, indicating that in

solution these bodies assume the same form (*cf.* Rao and Jatkar, *Proc. Indian Science Congress*, Allahabad, 1930, p. 225).

3. The heats of solution of two forms of triglycerides of trilaurin, tristearin and tripalmitin have been measured by the method of twin calorimeter.

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Dyes Derived from Acridic Acid.

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Acridic acid contains two carboxyl groups in *ortho* positions to one another, and is, therefore, expected to yield dyestuffs on condensation with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds in the same way as phthalic acid or quinolinic acid (Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1102). Recently Tewari and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 58) have successfully condensed quinoline-1:2:3-tricarboxylic acid with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds with the production of dyestuffs having interesting properties of colour and fluorescence. They could not condense acridic acid itself on account of the fact that at that time it was practically an inaccessible material, but nevertheless from theoretical considerations they came to the conclusion that dyes derived from acridic acid, even if they could be prepared, would have the same colour as the corresponding dyes derived from quinoline-1:2:3-tricarboxylic acid.

Acridine being now available in quantity, acridic acid was prepared from it by oxidation with potassium permanganate, and the acid condensed with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds in the usual manner with the production of dyestuffs. When compared with the corresponding dyes derived from quinoline-1:2:3-tricarboxylic acid